

A succinct view of wildlife crimes in West Bengal and their conservation practices

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Abstract

The wide range of wildlife animals in India is suffering from a combination of threats, which leads to suitable habitat loss, and increasing conflict between human and illegal wildlife trade that is pushing the wildlife population towards extinction. However, studies in India are showing that indiscriminate poaching and illegal trade are increasingly becoming the main drivers for the extinction of species. Recent, illegal wildlife trades have received attention from biological and conservation perspectives. In that context, the present reviewed the wildlife crimes in West Bengal and their conservation practices. The study reviewed the recent wildlife crimes in West Bengal and the conservation practices employed in West Bengal to save the wildlife species are also listed. The law enforcement and involvement of NGOs in the protection of wildlife are also itemized in detail and the actions which is taken by the Indian government against wildlife crimes are enumerated in detail. Following this, the impact caused by the occurrence of wildlife crimes is also discussed. Thus, the present study will guide future researchers about the wildlife crimes in West Bengal and the conservation practices, which are involved in animal protection. It also creates awareness among people regarding the impact of wildlife crimes and the measures taken against wildlife crimes.

Keywords: Wildlife Crimes, Wildlife Conservation, West Bengal, Wildlife (Protection) Act, Sundarban Wildlife Sanctuary.

Introduction

Wildlife crime for trade and subsistence is a serious threat to conservation. Various endangered species like Elephants, Asian big cats, and Rhinoceros are at the extinction edge if the present

wildlife trend is not stunted. The illegal trade of wildlife is among the foremost reason for the prompt decline of wildlife species. Human beings' misuse of biotic assets is the main cause of the debasement of the natural environment of various species, bringing about their fast eradication and decay. Throughout a couple of decades, over 10-20 per cent of all vertebrate species are in danger of elimination. Wildlife chasing towards business and subsistence purposes constitutes a significant risk to the survival of animals. Every year, in Southeast Asia, the illegal exchange of wildlife species exceeds billion of US dollars. The main challenge of global conservation is the illicit trade of wildlife. Various charismatic species like Rhinoceros, Tigre, and Snow Leopard are threatened with extinction. As an illustration, a century ago, the range of tigers was around 100,000, and at present, it has been reduced and only a few hundred are surviving. Likewise, from the beginning of the 20th century, the count of Rhinoceros also reduced drastically and more than 90% is abridged. Illegal hunting of Wildlife animals and the ecological and economical value of biota inhabitants is developing as a hazard across African Savannas. Owing to the secret nature of illicit crimes, which fallouts a few information that occurs as a drive for wild animal's meat industry.

Pumas and Jaguars are decreasing across the utmost of their assortment, normally due to habitat and hunting loss. The habitat loss influence is easier to assess than hunting, due to the latter occurs secretly and it is challenging to attain reliable crime pressure estimation. Since 2007, wildlife poaching, specifically Black Rhinos, White Rhinos, and African Elephants has been at the forefront of the conservation battle in Southern Africa. The increasing demand for Rhino ivory and Horn and the black market prices are also high in Asian Markets have simulated the poaching. The natural habitats of wildlife are being destroyed in the name of urbanization, industrialization, and globalization which leads to the development of lands and farming through humans. Illegal hunting and poaching to transnational illegal wildlife trafficking for jewellery, leather, medicines, fur, and meat are the utmost factors that contribute towards wildlife extinction. Illegal wildlife trade is recognized as one of the most significant criminal activities in the world, which brings billion-dollar profits in illegal trade. Each year millions of animals are caught leading to a decline in the species population on earth through an average of 40 per cent between the years 1970 and 2000.

If no severe conservation and awareness involvement by preventive lawful actions at both international and national stages are taken for saving wildlife, it could not be long before they

would be able to recognize a position only on the extinct species list. Not only that, but wildlife extinction would certainly have a huge impact on the human race also.

Wildlife crime may be termed as the illegal possession, movement, taking (or) trade of animals (or) their derivatives over the international, national and regional legislation contravention. Wildlife crimes in the form of poaching and wildlife trafficking in India ranked at 4th position for wildlife crimes and are valued at around 19 to 26 billion US dollars per year. According to a recent report, the United Nations Office (UNO) on crime and drugs stated that at least 132,144 captures of illicit international wildlife trade, comprising thousands of species were made across 120 nations in the past decade. Though not a major customer in the international illicit wildlife marketplace, 20% of all biota seizures documented during 1996-2008 took place in India. In 2009, Panna Tiger Reserve, in Central India lost all its tigers. Therefore, there has been a huge rise in Wildlife trafficking over recent periods. In that context, the present aims to view the recent wildlife crimes in West Bengal (WB), along with the conservation practices, which are taken to save wildlife species, and then the law and involvement of NGOs against wildlife crimes are also highlighted in this exploration.

The main objective of the present study is;

- To view the recent wildlife crimes in India, to plan an efficient conservation practice.
- To view the wildlife crimes that have taken place in WB from the past to still now, in the context of exploring the impacts caused by these activities.
- To view, Law enforcement and involvement of NGOs against wildlife trafficking, in a range of reviewing the advantages result from them.

Wildlife Crimes in India

Recent wildlife crimes in India are highlighted in section 2. Then, section 4, views the conservation practices in WB, to save the wildlife animals, and section 5, explores constraints in the conservation practices. A comparison of wildlife crimes in WB and other states is listed in section 6. The Law enforcement and involvement of NGOs' are listed in section 7. Actions taken by the Indian government against Wildlife crimes are shown in section 8. The impact results from wildlife crimes are enumerated in section 9. The entire paper is concluded in section 10.

In recent times, in the COVID-19 Pandemic situation, wildlife crimes in India have been amplified severely. Thus, the recent wildlife crimes that occurred in India are discussed in this section. The most recent census reported that India has 2,967 tigers. India is the home of the principal tiger

habitat and also resulted in premier tiger seizures globally (Jhala et al., 2021; Kumar, Awasthi, Qureshi, & Jhala, 2019). Likewise, various activities of humans have caused death to wildlife animals. Electric fencing along the Mechi River banks in Bahundangi Village of Nepal led numerous elephants to death, in the Naxalaberi-Kharibari belt enclosed in the Himalayan Kingdom (TNN, 2022a).

The report (Choudhury, 2022), stated that 40 exotic animals such as 30 tortoises, 55 crocodile hatchlings, 2 monkeys, 18 Sumatran Water Monitors, 2 Marmoset Monkeys, 22 Pythons, 1 Albino Wallaby, 4 Serval Cats, and 4 Flame Bowerbirds have been smuggled from Myanmar and this crime involved both the countries that are India (Mizoram) and Myanmar smugglers were involved. In a similar way, 24 Deer horns, pangolin scales, and 6 Monito Lizards' skin have been smuggled into Madhya Pradesh and it was seized by WWCB officials ("Madhya Pradesh: Wildlife officials bust poaching gang," 2021).

The Environmental Investigation Agency (EIA) reported that from 1994 to 2003, there were 684 tiger poaching cases. By this, India lost 1110 tigers from 1994 to 2016. The investigation (Krishnasamy, 2019) revealed that recently there were 369 tiger seizures in India, which is higher than in other tiger range countries. Tiger teeth, meat, fat, bones, skin, claws, and genitals have been poached for traditional medicines. The other parts such as tails, eyeballs, and whiskers were also utilized in medicine. The major cause for tiger seizures is to meet Chinese demand. The exploration (Paudel, Acharya, Baral, Heinen, & Jnawali, 2020) stated that the chief illicit trade pathway for tiger-body parts is through the Indo-China border. The scarcity of tiger parts is replaced by the leopards in the markets. The investigation (Sethi, Goyal, & Choudhary, 2019), between 2012 and 2016 stated that 650 leopards have been poached in India, resulting in both endangered fields being in danger. Numerous online reports gambled that the tiger poaching culminated during the Covid-19 lockdowns.

Recent Wildlife Crimes in West Bengal

The recent wildlife crimes taken place in WB are listed in this section. The report (BANERJEE, 2022) stated that 500 Indian Soft-Shell Turtles were found dead in a house at Swarupnagar in North 24 Parganas. Forest and Wildlife crime prevention officials have seized and arrested two traders. The team has also found 88 dead turtles along with alive ones. Some dead turtles had been in the form of shells detached from them and were killed for the meat. Then, the turtles are

produced under schedule I of the Wildlife protection act and were allegedly for being transported to various markets in Madhyamgram and Bongaon. From the investigation (Singh, 2022), 40 exotic wildlife such as 19 Primates were seized from two Delhi governments, that have been moving from Mizoram and were bound for Siliguri in Northern WB. The other animals involved are 13 small turtles, 3 exotics Birds, 2 Baby Wallabies, and 3 big Tortoises. The Indo-Pacific Finless Porpoises were the smallest whale species and they tend to live in shallow, coastal water. Over the past two years, various Indo-Pacific finless porpoise carcasses with fins ostensibly sliced off have been found in the East Midnapore district in Bengal.

Biologists team working along a beach stretch have found the carcasses. Moreover, at least 4 porpoises have been found with their fins chopped off. It has been found as unusual and there could be some illegal activities going on it has been flagged to Wildlife Crime Control Bureau - WCCB and the forest department ("Porpoises with fins allegedly chopped off found in West Bengal; probe ordered," 2022). The WB CID- Crime Investigation Department has arrested 4 persons for poaching 658 alive parakeets from Kolkata ("WCCB and Bengal CID bust wildlife illegal trade racket; 658 live parakeets found," 2022). The majority of seizures were reported during transit (or) attempting to sell (or) handover to a third party. Only 13 cases were reported for the domestic sale of tiger parts. The major domestic cases include the sale of teeth, claws, and paws. There have been reports of people attempting to sell tigers' skin in the Kolkata market and they have also attempted to sell fake tiger claws and skin for a high price. West Bengal forest department officials seized two elephants, which are being transported illegally to Gujarat (Choudhurri, 2021).

Likewise, the forest department of Howrah district and WCCB have recovered 4 ivory sculptures worth 10 crores of the Indian rupee. Also arrested as a suspect to be a middleman (Chakraborty, 2022). The foresters have recovered 4 kangaroos, including a carcass from Siliguri. It has been supposed that the animals were illegally transported to the bordering countries by North Bengal Hallway ("Forest squad to check trafficking & illegal trade," 2022). The article (Adhya, 2022) reported that three female fishing cats were killed in Bagnan, Howrah district. The carcasses are dumped in one place with their legs tied with plastic ropes. The medical report stated that there are no visible injuries in the bodies and from the carcass condition it has been found that there were killed over 3 to 4 days through poisoning. This scandalous occurrence appeared to be an

emblematic mockery demonstration in contradiction of long-term conservation struggles in the district.

Conservation Practices in West Bengal

India is home to 1,331 species of birds 837 have been found in Bengal. To preserve these various species, several conservation practices are made in west Bengal by Sundarban Wildlife sanctuary. This particular conversation reserve and other conservation reserves are discussed in this section.

Sundarban Wildlife Sanctuary

The Sundarbans National Park (SNP) is the tiger reserve, national park, and bio-sphere reserve in WB, India. It is a portion of the Ganges Delta of Sundarbans and neighbouring the Sundarban Reserve Forest (SRF) in Bangladesh. It is situated in the southwest of Bangladesh. This delta is compactly enclosed by mangrove forests. It is one of the major reserves of Bengal Tigers. Also, it is a home for various reptiles, birds, and invertebrates including the salt-water crocodile. The present SNP is declared as the core region of Sundarban Tiger Reserve in the year 1973 and as a wildlife sanctuary in 1977. It has been acknowledged as a national park in 1984, May 04 (Guha, 2020). In 1987, UNESCO inscribed SNP as a World Heritage site (Mistri & Das, 2020) and it has been labelled as a Ramsar Site since 2019 (Mahmood et al., 2021). Since 1989, it has been measured as the World Biosphere Reserve Network. The 1st forest administration separation for having jurisdiction in the SNP was established in 1869. In the year 1875, a huge mangrove forest part has been professed as a reserved forest under 1865, the Forest Act (Act VIII of 1865). The enduring area of the forests has been stated as a reserve forest in the subsequent years and the woods have been so far controlled through a civil government district which was positioned below the forest division control. A forest department that has the fundamental administration of forest and management unit which has been developed in the year 1879 with the head office in Khulna, Bangladesh. For the period 1893 to 1898, the first management plan has been written.

The geographical location of SNP is located between 21° 43' to 21° 55' North Latitude and between 88° 42' to 89° 04' East Longitude. The normal altitude of the SNP is 7.5 m above sea level. The SNP has been composed of 54 minor islands and is interconnected through various branches of the Ganges River. The climatic condition of SNP is, the extreme and lowest temperature is 48°C and 20° C correspondingly. Heavy rain and high moisture at 80 per cent as it is closer to the Bay of Bengal. The monsoon continues from the middle of June to the middle of September. The predominant airstream is from the northern and northeastern part throughout October to the middle of March and South-west westerlies succeed from the middle of March to

September. Storms that occasionally developed into cyclones were common from May to October (Woodward & Cooke, 2022).

Other Conservation Reserves

Diverse Eco-systems have been caused by the amusing fauna diversity of the WB which contains 10,013 species out of a total 89,451 species of animals present in India, therefore, representing 11.19% of the fauna. West Bengal has 4692 square kilometres of forest beneath a secured zone network that is 39.50 per cent of the WB verified forest region with the Pakhi Bitan WLS Jalpaiguri Region ensuring a zone of 14.09 sq. km, recently it has been acquainted WLS in the state, the overall area under Protected Area has gone up to 47,05. 9362 sq. km (Das, 2021). The protection area network involved 1502.8146 sq. km with 16 wildlife sanctuaries, 1981.4817 sq. km with 6 national parks along with this balance regions were being characterized through buffer zones of 2 reserves for tigers such as Buxa and Sundarbans tiger reserve. There have been two Elephant Reserves (ER) such as Mayrajaharna ER with an expanse of 414.00 sq. km and Eastern-Dooars ER with a range of 977.51sq.km (Mandal & Das Chatterjee, 2021). In addition to this, Bio-sphere Reserve is named Sundarban Biosphere Reserve with an area of 9630 sq. km. It comprises the Lothian Island Wildlife- Sanctuary, Haliday Island Wildlife Sanctuary, West Sundarban Wildlife Sanctuary, and Sundarban Tiger Reserve (Mitra et al., 2018).

An emphasis on WB has been provided to the management and conservation of defensible resources in a range of achieving the objective of long-term biodiversity conservation. The overall plan involved the protection of critical habitats of endangered wildlife species. The Bengal Wilderness is also home to a highly endangered species array such as Red Panda, Asian Elephant, Gaur, Great One Horned Rhino, Black Necked Crane, Serow, Goliath Heron, Great Pied Hornbill, Salvator Lizards, Estuarine Crocodile, Rare Batagur Terrapin, and Olive Ridley Marine Turtle let alone being the habitation for most of the Indian cats such as Clouded Leopard, Royal Bengal Tiger, Golden Cat, Marbled Cat, Jungle Cat and Fishing Cat demonstrating the smaller cats (Sen & Pattanaik, 2019).

Constraints in the conservation Practices

The constraints and challenges faced in the wide implementation of conservation practices are listed in this section. However, protection subsists in the SNP there are some ambiguities. The geographical topography with an intimidating environment traversed through various rivers and

their branches, along with a long transnational boundary with Bangladesh, inaugurates permitted illegal trafficking, illegal cutting of woods and fishing-trawlers, and disturbs mangrove forest. Shortage of infrastructure, funds, and staff intensified circumstances.

The Sunderban-Tiger-Reserve has various encounters with its upcoming functions. According to the Tigers that are wandering, the conflict between humans to tigers endured a problem. Tigers in Sunderban hunt people and it has been predicted that thousands of native people have been brutally killed by Sunderban tigers in the past 4 decades. An assessment of the number of tigers existing on the reserve by utilizing an advanced approach has not been completed yet. The tiger preservation strategy has been anticipated as constituents for the state equal direction-finding commission under the leadership of the chief minister (CM) and the reserve specifically the foundation of tiger Conservation (Mondal, Thakur, Juliev, & Kumar De, 2021).

At present, the ecosystem in Sundarbans is under pollution threat due to the high pressure of anthropogenic activities around and inside the Sundarbans such as pollution, urbanization, industrialization, tourism, water vessels capsizing, navigation, intensive farming using agrochemicals, and carrying goods. All of these processes might affect the water, soil, and air quality of Sundarbans which could ultimately affect the quality and health of the terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems of the forest (Mahmood et al., 2021).

Comparison of Wildlife crimes in WB vs Other States

Table 1 shows the wildlife crimes that are happening in West Bengal and other states, how the animals were trafficked and poached by the smugglers.

Table 1. Wildlife crimes in WB and other states.

Ref	Animal/ Bird	State and Country	Year	Reason / Act
("Bengal tops in illegal wildlife trade in eastern India, int'l gangs most active," 2018)	Slow loris / Pied hornbills	West Bengal, India	2018	Many foreign-origin species were smuggled into India because of the hefty price.
("WCCB and Bengal CID bust wildlife illegal trade racket; 658 live parakeets found," 2021)	Parakeets	West Bengal, India	2021	According to schedule IV of the Wildlife (Protection) Act, 1972. Capturing and selling the parakeets is considered a crime.

("The Big Picture Of Wildlife Trafficking," 2022)	Alexandrine, Plum-headed parakeets and Rose-ringed	Delhi, India	2022	These three parakeets were trafficked mostly in the countries
("Bengal forest guards rescue 2 Arunachal elephants being trafficked to Gujarat," 2021)	Elephants	West Bengal, India	2021	An elephant is the main species that are poached and trafficked for its tusks.
("On same day, 3 elephants die in 2 Odisha districts," 2021)	Elephants	Odisha, India	2021	Elephants are poisoned and electrocuted by the poachers
("Bad News: There Are Kangaroos in West Bengal Forests," 2022)	Kangaroos	West Bengal, India	2022	Kangaroos belong to Australia and New Guinea, but these animals were smuggled and left in the forests.
(Adhya, 2022)	Three Female Fishing Cats	West Bengal, India	2022	Wildlife Protection Act, 1972 under Schedule 1
(BANERJEE, 2022)	500 Indian Soft Shell Turtles	West Bengal, India	2022	Killed for meat / Wildlife Protection Act, 1972 Schedule 1
(S, 2022)	Aldabra Tortoises, De Brazza Monkeys, Tarsier Monkeys, Armadillos, White Porcupines, Iguanas, Ball Pythons, Sugar Gliders, and Marmosets	Tamil Nadu, India	2022	Customs Act
(REDDY, 2022)	26 Pieces of Ivory Jeweler	Telangana, India	2022	Wildlife Protection Act, 1972 under Schedule 9
(OPPILI, 2022)	2,200 live start Tortoises	Tamil Nadu, India	2022	Wildlife Protection Act, 1972 under Schedule 4

The table clearly explains the reasons for the animals that have been trafficked in the forest areas, and how the animals are dying because of climate change, pollution, and deforestation. Not only Indian animals and birds but various birds and animals were also smuggled from many countries. The habitual nature of the animals is changed and the smuggling rate increases because of the urge to have wild animals as pets and for food as meat. Due to the reason of meat-eating habits.

Recently, most of the wildlife crimes are from West Bengal, the acts that are established by the governments to protect animals from smugglers and various hazards.

Law Enforcement and Involvement of NGOs'

The National Green Tribunal (NGT) on October 18th, 2010 established the expeditious and effective disposal of cases that are relating to forest conservation and protection of the environment along with other natural resources that include the enforcement of any legal right (Gill, 2020). The legal right which relates to the environment gives compensation for the damages to the property and person and gives relief. Along with the matters that are connected to therewith or incidental thereto. The Law Division and Policy monitors the cases in the court which pertain to the Ministry of Forests, Climate change, and Environment. In the Ministry of Legal Monitor cell, the effective way of monitoring the court cases has been set under the Public Interest Litigation Division and along with that a centralized management system of court cases has developed.

The active participation of India in the conferences of UNESCO and the impact of that international conferences resulted in the importance of the amendments in the Constitution of India, using the article 51-A (g) the fundamental duties were imposed on the citizens to protect and improve the nature of the environment which includes lakes, wildlife, forest, and rivers. The U/A- 48 – A was directly given to states to protect and improve the nature of the environment and to guard the forests and the country's wildlife. Most significantly the subject's wildlife and forest were shifted from the list of states to the seventh schedule of the concurrent list. This enables the parliament to make laws on the subjects. Another result of the Stockholm conference, in 1972 Indian government formed the advisory body National Committee on Environmental Planning and Co-ordination (NCEPC). The whole task of this committee is to advise the government about its environmental matters. The city-based NGO Society for Heritage and Ecological Research (SHER), with the University of West Bengal and the Scottish Church College, will hold the next season of certificate courses in biodiversity conversation and wildlife changes in climates (TNN, 2022b).

The civil law makes this act a unique piece of legislation, specifically the Land Acquisition Act of 1894 with the subsequent revisions, the criminal law and the power management of different functions of the Department of the Forest are featured in the single legislation. The next unique

aspect of the legislation as it doesn't make any distinction between the actual act and the attempt. Hence this proves that the WPA of 1972 is very firm.

To investigate the Wildlife (Protection) Act, in 1972 the case provisions the act along with the procedure of the Code of Criminal provisions. In 1973, the need to be applied in the time of search, seizure, and arrest. This provides punishment for the offences among other things that include altering the boundaries of the national park or a sanctuary, hunting, offences that are related to the core area of the Tiger Reserve, trade and illegal possession of wild animals and their derivatives, and the articles. In most such offences the quantum punishment is the jail term of three years and this might also extend to seven years, thereby making these offences cognizable and non-bailable. The board of WB Biodiversity formed the w.e.f on September 16, 2004, which compliance with the Act of Biological Diversity in 2002, as the statutory body which comes under the Environment department, in the Government of WB. The functions of the WBBB ensure the proper implementation of 2002, Biological Diversity Act.

In 2005, the WB Biological Diversity rules were framed and in 2006 27th January the w.e.f in the exercise of the power it conferred by the 63rd section of the Biological Diversity Act. This confers the legal purview to restrict to use of the biological resources of the State by Indian citizens. The WB Biodiversity board has made it mandatory for Indian citizens to seek to obtain the biological sources that occur in knowledge associated with or in the State, for the bio-utilization and bio-survey or commercial utilization.

The Directors of the National Training Centre for Dogs and Animals (NTCD&A) said that the training program of the wildlife sniffer dog has been carefully planned to train and accommodate detection skills and obedience specified for the curbing of the illegal wild trade and detection in India. This 10th batch of the six young German Shepherd dogs they were ranged from six to nine months old. The 12 handlers began the seven-month courses at their Basic Training Centre, the Indo-Tibetan Border Police Force (BTC-ITBP) camp in Haryana (TRAFFIC, 2022).

Actions Taken by the Indian Government

India welcomed eight cheetahs from Namibia as a part of the program, this helped to reintroduce the feline in the country that declared in 1952 that it was extinct. An aircraft that is modified Boeing by carrying the cheetahs, especially in crates of wood, landed at the Gwalior airbase in Madhya

Pradesh. The animals were brought under the MoU reported (India, 2022a) that they were flown to Kuno National Park.

The state government is completely committed to the wildlife, grasslands, wetlands, and forests which need to be conserved. The government works in collaboration with wildlife organizations, experts, and lovers. During this time, Chief Minister Ashok Gehlot called a meeting at the residence of the Chief Minister in Jaipur as reported in (India, 2022b). It has been stated that wildlife conservation is the top priority of the government and the state of the government took many efforts to increase the number of tigers as it exceeded 100. Along with that, the numbers of the other wildlife animals life were also increased such as Chital, Deer, and Blackbuck. In the meeting, the chief minister directed the officers of the department to work accordingly to the requirements in the sanctuary of the states that include Sariska, Ramgarh Vishdhari, Ranthambore, and Mukundra.

In the report (PINJARKAR, 2022), it is discussed to take note of the frequent deaths of tigers and elephants in collisions with trains as the railway minister Ashwini Vaishnav asked all the zones to build a permanent mitigation that structures the measures which underpasses and overpasses in 100 locations across the country. As the cases that relate to the landscapes of elephants and tigers. This was discussed in many collisions between the wildlife and the train that occurs at curves. The ministers advised identifying those locations and realigning the railway lines accordingly to avoid such situations in the future, this would be beneficial for wildlife and railways.

It is reported in ("WB: Forest officers seize leopard, red panda skins in Jalpaiguri, 3 arrested," 2022) that the forest department officially seized a leopard skin and three red panda skins at Jalpaiguri. They also arrested 3 persons who might be with connections. The residents which are accused of Nepal have been produced in the court. Then, 11 persons were allegedly involved in the smuggling and they have been arrested. The department of forest already seized leopard skin and elephant's tusk along with the pangolin and gecko scales in months. The government of Bengal decided to form a special squad for a forest to prevent the crimes that are happening in wildlife that includes trafficking of wildlife in the northern part of Bengal and poaching that follows to spate the recoveries of the parts of the animal, carcass the wild animals to arrest the traffickers in the regions ("Forest squad to check trafficking & illegal trade," 2022).

Global Impact of Wildlife Crimes

The cheetahs were globally listed as vulnerable in the International Union of the conservation of red list of Nature threatened species. Presently they only remain 7000 primarily in African savannas (India, 2022a). Human activity wiped out an average of 69% of the wildlife of the world under 50 years. Based on the report published by World Wildlife Fund (WWF) ("Human Activity Has Wiped Out Nearly 70% Of World's Wildlife In Just 50 Years: Report," 2022). The world's population of wildlife has declined since the 1970s as they have reduced to a two-third level. The ocean and forest have been polluted, this report tells that the world is emptying and nature is unravelling. The WWF reported ("Global Wildlife Populations Have Sunk 69% Since 1970: Report," 2022) that the data which is used by the Zoological Society of London on the status of the 32,000 population in wildlife covers more than 5000 species. This report stated that the population size has decreased by 69%. Pollution, Human exploitation, climate change, and deforestation became the biggest drivers of loss. The population of Wildlife in the Caribbean and Latin America was hit hard and experienced a 94% drop in the five decades. The Brazilian Amazon plummeted by 65% of the pink river dolphins between the years 1994 and 2016. These reports were similar to the WWT of the last assessment done in the year 2020. So this makes to conclude that the population of wildlife is continuing to decline at the rate of 2.5% each year.

Conclusion

Wildlife crimes have happened for a range of purposes like healthcare, ornamentation, and food. Most of the wildlife trade was legal which contributed to the livelihood and income generation for numerous people comprising some of the poorest people in the world. Conversely, the fragment of wildlife harvesting and trading befalls outer the laws was determined as the chief threat to conservation after habitat loss and over-exploitation. Therefore, the present study reviewed the recent wildlife crimes in West Bengals. The conservation practices and their constraints in WB were also reviewed in the study. Then, the comparison was performed on the wildlife crimes in WB and other states in India. The Law enforcement and Involvement of NGOs against Wildlife Crimes were also deliberated in this paper. Followed by this, the action taken by the Indian Government against Wildlife Crimes was also enumerated. Finally, the impact caused by this wildlife crime globally was also listed. From this study, it was suggested that more conservation practices need to be implemented in the WB and the people around the area should be educated

about the need for protecting wildlife animals. Along with this, awareness should be created among the people about the acts implemented against wildlife crimes by the Indian Government.

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